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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) and Copper(II) with 2,6-Pyridinediol

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SOME of the hydroxypyridines are used widely as analytical reagents in the determination of different metal ions¹⁻⁵. The present communication reports the use of 2,6-pyridinediol as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Experimental

Double-distilled water and A. R. grade chemicals were used. Stock solutions of ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate and 2,6-pyridinediol (Aldrich) were prepared in double-distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the chloride or nitrate salts of cations, and from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of anions.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using an Universal 14 spectrophotometer. pH measurements were made using an Elico pH meter.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 1–84 µg of Fe^{II} or 1.2–116 µg of Cu^{II}, were added 20 times of 2,6-pyridinediol solution in case of Fe^{II} system and 15 times in case of Cu^{II} system, and pH values of the solutions was adjusted to 7–10.2 and 7.5–10.8 respectively. In case of Fe^{II}, the solution was heated for 0.5 h while for Cu^{II} no heating was required. For both the ions, the volume was made upto 20 ml by adding double-distilled water, and absorbance was measured at 420 and 535 nm in case of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively, against the reagent blank, and the amount evaluated by a calibration curve.

Results and Discussions

When aqueous solutions of Cu^{II} and 2,6-pyridinediol were mixed at different concentrations and at different pH values formation of the coloured

complex took place immediately. In case of Fe^{II}, while following same procedure, no coloured complex was formed in cold but when the solution was heated on a water-bath for 30 min, formation of the coloured complex took place. The absorption spectra of different systems were recorded and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF Fe^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES WITH 2,6-PYRIDINEDIOL

Characteristic	Fe ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
λ_{max} (nm)	420	535
Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^3$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	10.8	14.2
Reagent needed	20 times	15 times
pH range	7–10.2	7.5–10.8
Beer's law range (ppm)	upto 4.8	upto 6.6
Range of determination (ppm)	0.5–4.2	0.6–5.8
Metal–ligand ratio (Jobs method)	1 : 2	1 : 2
Standard deviation (Metal ion concn., ppm)	0.0078 (3.5)	0.0042 (3.0)

Effect of diverse ions: The study was carried out in solutions containing 3.5 ppm of Fe^{II} or Cu^{II} and in presence of the desired amounts of foreign ions. After following the recommended procedure the absorbance was noted. The tolerance limits (in parenthesis, ppm) of different anions and cations in determinations of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} are as follows: for both Fe and Cu, fluoride (100), chloride (1000), bromide (1500), EDTA (5), Zn^{II} (50), Cd^{II} (100), Hg^{II} (500), Mn^{II} (200), Co^{II} (100) and Ni^{II} (100); for Fe only, nitrate (500), thiosulphate (20) and Cu^{II} (1.5); for Cu only, nitrate (1000), thiosulphate (10) and Fe^{II} (100).

Applications: The method was applied in the determination of iron and copper in their alloys. The solutions of the alloys were prepared as described in literature⁶. In each case, six determinations were made. Analysis of N. K. K. 920 alloy gave iron content 0.718% (0.72% certified value) with a standard deviation of 0.01. In brass, Cu content was found to be 64.983% (65.0% certified value) with a standard deviation 0.007.

Comparison with other reagents: A comparison with other spectrophotometric reagents shows that 2,6-pyridinediol ranks among the highly sensitive reagents (Table 2).

TABLE 2—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC REAGENTS FOR Fe^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH 2,6-PYRIDINEDIOL

Metal ion	Reagent	Molar absorptivity dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Fe ^{II}	Methyl-2-pyridyl ketoxime ^a	14.0 × 10 ³
	Biacetylmonoxime thiosemicarbazone ^b	11.5 × 10 ³
	4-Amino-2-mercapto-5-nitroso-6-pyrimidinediol ^c	6.1 × 10 ³
	5-Chloro-2,3-pyridinediol ^d	2.5 × 10 ³
Cu ^{II}	Biacetylmonoxime semicarbazone ^e	10.1 × 10 ³
	Benzimidazole-2-carboxanilide oxime ^f	14.5 × 10 ³
	4-Imino-1,3-dimethylalloxan-5-oxime ^g	5.1 × 10 ³
	Rutin ^h	8.1 × 10 ³
	Ortho aminophenol ⁱ	10.6 × 10 ³

^aRef. 7, ^bRef. 8, ^cRef. 9, ^dRef. 10, ^eRef. 11, ^fRef. 12, ^gRef. 13, ^hRef. 14, ⁱRef. 15.

It is apparent that the present method, besides being highly sensitive, is very simple to carry out as no extraction and no multiplicity of solvents are required.

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Isonitrosothiocamphor as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Rhodium(III)

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ISONITROSOTHIOCAMPHOR (INTC) has been reported as an analytical reagent for palladium¹, cobalt² and copper³. At room temperature rhodium(III) shows no colour reaction with the reagent but forms a red chelate with INTC while heating on a boiling water-bath. The complex is extractable into chloroform. Taking advantage of this phenomenon, a simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of rhodium has been developed.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer fitted with stoppered quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length. A ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used to measure acidity of the aqueous solution.

Isonitrosothiocamphor was prepared as reported⁴ and a 0.4% solution of the reagent in ethanol was used. All other reagent used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared

from RhCl₃.3H₂O (Johnson & Matthey) followed by standardisation⁵. The solution was further diluted as required. Chloroform was distilled before use.

General procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing 50–150 μg of rhodium(III) was added the INTC solution (0.5 ml) followed by addition of a buffer solution (pH 3). The volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10 ml. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 10 min, cooled to room temperature and then equilibrated with of chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The separated organic layer was dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 345 nm against a reagent blank. Rhodium was determined from a calibration curve. To test the interferences, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of rhodium complex was investigated in the pH range 0–10. Chloroform extracts showed maximum and steady absorbance when the extractions were carried out at pH 2–4. When the extraction was repeated using the same aqueous phase after a single extraction, the organic extract virtually showed no absorbance. It indicate a quantitative recovery of rhodium in this pH range.

The Rh^{III}–INTC complex in chloroform exhibits absorption maximum at 345 nm with a broad band around 470 nm. The reagent blank shows insignificant absorbance from 340 nm onwards. Wavelength 345 nm was selected for all analytical measurements.

The optimum reagent concentration was ascertained by extracting Rh^{III} at various concentrations of INTC. It was found that 0.5 ml of 0.4% ethanolic solution of INTC was sufficient to extract 50–150 μg of Rh^{III} in a single extraction; higher reagent concentration had no adverse effect, but was avoided because of the higher absorbance of the blank. The mole-ratio method indicated the formation of a 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) complex under the experimental conditions.

The effect of diverse ions on rhodium(III) determination was studied by carrying out the extraction at pH 3.0. Deviation of not more than ±3% from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the respective diverse ion. In the estimation of 97.5 μg Rh, the following ions did not interfere when present in amounts (mg shown in parenthesis) : Ca^{II} (8), Ba^{II} (9), Sr^{II} (8.5), Zr^{IV} (7), Th^{IV} (6), Mn^{II} (3), Cd^{II} (4), Zn^{II} (9), Mg^{II} (10), U^{VI} (4), Cr^{III} (2), Al^{III} (10), Pb^{II} (3), As^{III} (8), La^{III} (10). Ni^{II} (2.5) and Co^{II} (0.5) could be tolerated in presence of EDTA. Cu^{II} (2.5) was masked with tartrate. Pd^{II} (0.5) was harmless in presence of ammonium hydrogen fluoride caused less recovery of rhodium. Less than 0.1 mg each of Mo and V could be tolerated. Pt^{IV} was co-extracted with Rh^{III} and thus showed high results. Hg^{II} must be absent. Among the anions, 10 mg each of borate,